

The Mathematics Education
Volume-LIX, No. 3, September 2025

ISSN 0047-6269

Journal website: <https://internationaljournalsiwan.com/Mathematic.php>

ORCID Link: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7467-6080>

International Impact Factor: **7.75** <https://impactfactorservice.com/home/journal/2295>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=UOfM8B4AAAAJ>

Refereed and Peer-Reviewed Quarterly Journal

Novel Probability Based Similarity Measure of Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets and Its Application in Clustering

by **Manas Singh Sakrwar***, *Research Scholar,*

Department of Mathematics,

Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur-495001, India

*Corresponding author: manassingh0826@outlook.com

(Received: August 5, 2025; Accepted: September 5, 2025;

Published Online: September 30, 2025)

Abstract:

This paper extends the probabilistic similarity measure from Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (IFSs) to Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets (PFSs), which offer a more flexible framework for modeling uncertainty. We define a new similarity measure specifically for PFSs and construct a corresponding similarity matrix to capture the relationships among PFS based data. Based on this, we propose a novel method for determining the λ -cut of the equivalence relation derived from the similarity matrix. This leads to the development of a new clustering algorithm that leverages the equivalence relation on PFSs to identify meaningful clusters.

The proposed algorithm is evaluated using datasets appropriate for PFS modeling and is compared with existing fuzzy clustering methods. Experimental results show that our approach performs better in terms of clustering representation.

Keywords: Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets, Probabilistic Similarity, Relation Based Clustering

1. Introduction:

Clustering is a fundamental task in data analysis that aims to group similar objects based on shared characteristics. In fuzzy set theory, one approach to clustering relies on fuzzy similarity relations instead of a strict equivalence. The idea of similarity provides a more generalized framework for comparison [1]. While crisp equivalence relations have been widely used for clustering, their fuzzy analogs fuzzy equivalence relations also provide a robust frame work [2]. However, in practical applications, the resulting relations are often fuzzy similarity relations rather than strict fuzzy equivalence relations, presenting a long-standing challenge in clustering tasks [3, 4]. To address this, researchers commonly apply transitive closure methods to transform similar ity into equivalence relations. Several enhancements, such as optimal fuzzy equivalence relations, fuzzy trees, and FCMBP, have been proposed [5], al though many of these methods remain complex or approximate in nature [6].

Intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs), introduced by Atanassov [7], offer a richer framework by accounting for both membership and non-membership degrees. Li et al. [8] demonstrated that the set of all IFS equivalence relations forms a complete lattice, laying the foundation for structural analysis. Building on this, Lohani and Kar [9] introduced a probabilistic similarity measure (PSM) and proposed the PIFCM clustering algorithm. Further contributions include new correlation coefficients and similarity measures that enhance clustering accuracy in intuitionistic fuzzy environments [10, 11, 12].

Pythagorean fuzzy sets (PFSs) extend IFSs by allowing greater flexibility in modeling uncertainty, constrained by the condition that the squared sum of membership and non-membership degrees does not exceed one. Zhang et al. [13] introduced a hierarchical clustering approach using PFSs, incorporating a dissimilarity degree between clusters. Peng and Yang [14] developed decision-making algorithms under PFSs, while Yager [15] proposed a level set representation for PFSs, opening new avenues for clustering and analysis in high-uncertainty environments.

This paper introduces a new probability-based similarity measure for Pythagorean fuzzy sets (PFSs), extending a concept previously limited to intuitionistic fuzzy sets. We leverage the enhanced expressive power of PFSs to create a more flexible model for uncertainty. Using this new measure, we perform clustering based on a novel λ -cut concept applied to a Pythagorean fuzzy equivalence matrix.

2. Preliminaries:

Pythagorean fuzzy sets are generalization of intuitionistic fuzzy set where unlike intuitionistic fuzzy where membership and non-membership are related by linear inequality they are related by squared based inequality.

Definition 1: [16] Let Ω be non-empty universal set. A Pythagorean fuzzy set (PFS) U on Ω is defined by a membership function $\mu_U : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and a non-membership function $\nu_U : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1]$. For every $\omega \in \Omega$, these function satisfy:

$$0 \leq (\mu_U(\omega))^2 + (\nu_U(\omega))^2 \leq 1;$$

A PFS U is denoted as $U = \{\langle \omega, \mu_U(\omega), \nu_U(\omega) \rangle \mid \omega \in \Omega\}$.

The hesitation degree $\pi_U(\omega)$ is given by $\pi_U(\omega) = \sqrt{(\mu_U(\omega))^2 + (\nu_U(\omega))^2}$

Definition 2: [17] A Pythagorean fuzzy Distance measure is a map

$$d : \text{PFS} \times \text{PFS} \rightarrow [0, 1],$$

which satisfies following properties for $U_1, U_2, U_3 \in \text{PFS}$:

1. $0 \leq d(U_1, U_2) \leq 1$,
2. $d(U_1, U_2) = 0$ iff $U_1 = U_2$,
3. $d(U_1, U_2) = d(U_2, U_1)$,
4. If $U_1 \subseteq U_2 \subseteq U_3$, where $U_1, U_2, U_3 \in \text{PFS}$, then $d(U_1, U_3) \geq d(U_1, U_2)$ and $d(U_1, U_3) \geq d(U_2, U_3)$.

Definition 3: [18] A Pythagorean fuzzy similarity measure is a map

$$\bar{s} : \text{PFS} \times \text{PFS} \rightarrow [0, 1],$$

which satisfies following properties for $U_1, U_2, U_3 \in \text{PFS}$:

1. $0 \leq \bar{s}(U_1, U_2) \leq 1$,
2. $\bar{s}(U_1, U_2) = \bar{s}(U_2, U_1)$
3. $\bar{s}(U_1, U_2) = 1$ iff $U_1 = U_2$,
4. If $U_1 \subseteq U_2 \subseteq U_3$, where $U_1, U_2, U_3 \in \text{PFS}$, then $\bar{s}(U_1, U_3) \leq \bar{s}(U_1, U_2)$
and $\bar{s}(U_1, U_3) \leq \bar{s}(U_2, U_3)$.

Definition 4: [19] Correlation coefficient between U_1 and U_2 where $U_1, U_2 \in \text{PFS}$ is map

$$\rho : \text{PFS} \times \text{PFS} \rightarrow [0, 1],$$

which satisfies following properties:

1. $\rho(U_1, U_2) = \rho(U_2, U_1)$,
2. $\rho(U_1, U_2) = 1$ iff $U_1 = U_2$,

When we use general form of statistics correlation coefficient is present in Pythagorean fuzzy setting. The correlation coefficient denoted by

$$\rho_{12} = \rho(U_1, U_2) = \frac{\phi(U_1, U_2)}{\sqrt{\psi(U_1) \psi(U_2)}}$$

We use the notation $\rho_{ij} = \rho(U_i, U_j)$ for convenience, and this will be applied consistently across all sections.

Definition 5: [20] An Pythagorean fuzzy similarity degree is map

$$s : \text{PFS} \times \text{PFS} \rightarrow \text{PFS},$$

such that it satisfies following properties for $U_1, U_2 \in \text{PFS}$;

1. $s(U_1, U_2) \in \text{PFS}$,
2. $s(U_1, U_2) = (1, 0)$ iff $U_1 = U_2$,
3. $s(U_1, U_2) = s(U_2, U_1)$.

We use the notation $s_{ij} = s(U_i, U_j)$ for convenience, and this will be applied consistently across all sections.

Definition 6: Let $U = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_p\}$ be a family of Pythagorean fuzzy sets defined on the universal set Ω . The matrix $S = [s_{ij}]_{p \times p}$, representing the Pythagorean fuzzy similarity degrees between the sets in U , is said to be a Pythagorean fuzzy equivalence matrix if it satisfies the following properties:

1. Reflexivity : $s_{ii} = (1, 0)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$.
2. Symmetry : $s_{ij} = s_{ji}$.
3. Transitivity: $S^2 \subseteq S$ i.e. $\bigvee_{k=1}^p (s_{ik} \wedge s_{kj}) \leq s_{ij}$, for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, p$.

3. Probabilistic Similarity Measure For Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets:

Definition 7: A distance measure is given based on euclidean distance introduced by Zhang [13] between two PFSs U_1 and U_2 as follows:

$$d(U_1, U_2) = \left[\frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_{U_1}^2(\omega_i) - \mu_{U_2}^2(\omega_i))^\gamma + (v_{U_1}^2(\omega_i) - v_{U_2}^2(\omega_i))^\gamma + (\pi_{U_1}^2(\omega_i) - \pi_{U_2}^2(\omega_i))^\gamma \right]^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}$$

$$= \left[\frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + (v_{1i}^2 - v_{2i}^2)^\gamma + (\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma \right]^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \quad (1)$$

Note: In the above equation, we use the simplified notations $\mu_{ij} = \mu_{U_i}(\omega_j)$, $v_{ij} = v_{U_i}(\omega_j)$, and $\pi_{ij} = \pi_{U_i}(\omega_j)$ for convenience. These notations will be adopted consistently throughout this paper and in all subsequent sections.

Definition 8: Let the probability of occurrence for $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_N\}$ are p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N respectively. Then, an Pythagorean fuzzy event U from Ω is specified through defining $p_{\min}(U)$ and $p_{\max}(U)$,

$$p_{\min}(U) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \mu_U^2(\omega_i), \quad p_{\max}(U) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \mu_U^2(\omega_i) + \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \pi_U^2(\omega_i) \quad (2)$$

Similarly, we can define

$$q_{\min}(U) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i v_U^2(\omega_i), \quad q_{\max}(U) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i v_U^2(\omega_i) + \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \pi_U^2(\omega_i) \quad (3)$$

So $p(U) \in [p_{\min}(U), p_{\max}(U)]$ and $q(U) \in [q_{\min}(U), q_{\max}(U)]$

Now for given two PFSs U_1 and U_2 we define new notations

$$p_{12}^l = \max(p_{\min}(U_1), p_{\min}(U_2))$$

$$p_{12}^u = \min(p_{\max}(U_1), p_{\max}(U_2))$$

$$q_{12}^l = \max(q_{\min}(U_1), q_{\min}(U_2))$$

$$q_{12}^u = \min(q_{\max}(U_1), q_{\max}(U_2))$$

Definition 9: Probabilistic distance measure between PFSs U_1 and U_2 for any $\gamma \geq 1$ is

$$d_\gamma(U_1, U_2) = \left[\frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N p_{12} (\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + q_{12} (v_{1i}^2 - v_{2i}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12} (\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma \right]^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \quad (4)$$

where $p_{12} \in [p_{12}^l, p_{12}^u]$, $q_{12} \in [q_{12}^l, q_{12}^u]$ and ρ_{12} is the correlation coefficient between U_1 and U_2 .

In this paper, we use the correlation coefficient proposed by Garg [21], defined as:

$$\rho_{12} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_{1i}^2 \mu_{2i}^2) + (\nu_{1i}^2 \nu_{2i}^2) + (\pi_{1i}^2 \pi_{2i}^2)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_{1i}^4 + \nu_{1i}^4 + \pi_{1i}^4)} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_{2i}^4 + \nu_{2i}^4 + \pi_{2i}^4)}} \quad (5)$$

Theorem 1: Let U_1 and U_2 be any two Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets (PFSs) defined on a universe of discourse Ω . The similarity degree between U_1 and U_2 , denoted by $\bar{s}(U_1, U_2)$, is bounded by the following inequality:

$$1 - \sqrt[\lambda]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \leq \bar{s}(U_1, U_2) \leq 1 - \sqrt[\lambda]{d_*(U_1, U_2)}$$

where $d^*(U_1, U_2)$ and $d_*(U_1, U_2)$ are given by:

$$d^*(U_1, U_2) = p_{12}^+ |\mu_{1r}^2 - \mu_{2r}^2|^\gamma + q_{12}^+ |\nu_{1r}^2 - \nu_{2r}^2|^\gamma + \rho_{12}^+ |\pi_{1r}^2 - \pi_{2r}^2|^\gamma$$

$$d_*(U_1, U_2) = p_{12}^- |\mu_{1s}^2 - \mu_{2s}^2|^\gamma + q_{12}^- |\nu_{1s}^2 - \nu_{2s}^2|^\gamma + \rho_{12}^- |\pi_{1s}^2 - \pi_{2s}^2|^\gamma$$

The coefficients for these distances satisfy the following conditions: $p_{12}^+ + q_{12}^+ + \rho_{12}^+ = 1$ and $p_{12}^- + q_{12}^- + \rho_{12}^- = 1$.

Proof: For $\lambda \geq 1$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} [d_\gamma(U_1, U_2)]^\gamma &= \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N p_{12}(\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1i}^2 - \nu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2N} N \max_i [p_{12}(\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1i}^2 - \nu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma] \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \max_i [p_{12}(\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1i}^2 - \nu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} [p_{12}(\mu_{1r}^2 - \mu_{2r}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1r}^2 - \nu_{2r}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1r}^2 - \pi_{2r}^2)^\gamma] \end{aligned}$$

where $\omega_r \in \Omega$ denotes the element for which the expression

$$p_{12}(\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1i}^2 - \nu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma$$

attains its maximum value.

$$\text{Take } S = \frac{p_{12} + q_{12} + \rho_{12}}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{2S} [p_{12}(\mu_{1s}^2 - \mu_{2s}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1s}^2 - \nu_{2s}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1s}^2 - \pi_{2s}^2)^\gamma] \\
& \leq \frac{|d_\gamma(U_1, U_2)|^\gamma}{S} \\
& \leq \frac{1}{2S} [p_{12}(\mu_{1r}^2 - \mu_{2r}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1r}^2 - \nu_{2r}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1r}^2 - \pi_{2r}^2)^\gamma] \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

S is used for normalizing the p_{12} , q_{12} and ρ_{12} . So p'_{12} , q'_{12} and ρ'_{12} value respective values after normalization.

$$\begin{aligned}
d^*(U_1, U_2) &= \max_{p_{12}, q_{12}} \{p'_{12}|\mu_{1r}^2 - \mu_{2r}^2|^\gamma + q'_{12}|\nu_{1r}^2 - \nu_{2r}^2|^\gamma + \rho'_{12}|\pi_{1r}^2 - \pi_{2r}^2|^\gamma\} \\
&= p_{12}^+|\mu_{1r}^2 - \mu_{2r}^2|^\gamma + q_{12}^+|\nu_{1r}^2 - \nu_{2r}^2|^\gamma + \rho_{12}^+|\pi_{1r}^2 - \pi_{2r}^2|^\gamma \quad (7)
\end{aligned}$$

After normalizing the original values p_{12}^u , q_{12}^u and ρ_{12}^u , we obtain the coefficients p_{12}^+ , q_{12}^+ and ρ_{12}^+ which sum to 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
d_*(U_1, U_2) &= \min_{p_{12}, q_{12}} \{p'_{12}|\mu_{1s}^2 - \mu_{2s}^2|^\gamma + q'_{12}|\nu_{1s}^2 - \nu_{2s}^2|^\gamma + \rho'_{12}|\pi_{1s}^2 - \pi_{2s}^2|^\gamma\} \\
&= p_{12}^-|\mu_{1s}^2 - \mu_{2s}^2|^\gamma + q_{12}^-|\nu_{1s}^2 - \nu_{2s}^2|^\gamma + \rho_{12}^-|\pi_{1s}^2 - \pi_{2s}^2|^\gamma \quad (8)
\end{aligned}$$

After normalizing the original values p_{12}^l , q_{12}^l and ρ_{12}^l , we obtain the coefficients p_{12}^- , q_{12}^- and ρ_{12}^- which sum to 1.

Now, we can rewrite Equation 6 as:

$$d_*(U_1, U_2) \leq \frac{[d_\gamma(U_1, U_2)]^\gamma}{S} \leq d^*(U_1, U_2).$$

Taking the γ -th root and subtracting from 1 throughout the inequality, we obtain:

$$1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \leq 1 - \frac{d_\gamma(U_1, U_2)}{\sqrt[\gamma]{S}} \leq 1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)}.$$

Let us define the similarity measure

$$\bar{s}(U_1, U_2) = 1 - \frac{d_\gamma(U_1, U_2)}{\sqrt[\gamma]{S}},$$

then the inequality can be rewritten as

$$1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \leq \bar{s}(U_1, U_2) \leq 1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)}.$$

Theorem 2: Let U_1 and U_2 be two Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets (PFSs), then, the function $s(U_1, U_2)$ defined below is a probabilistic similarity measure of Pythagorean fuzzy sets:

$$s_{12} = s(U_1, U_2) = \left(\left(1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (9)$$

Proof: Given the condition that $p_{12} + q_{12} + \rho_{12} = 1$, following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq p_{12}(\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + q_{12}(\nu_{1i}^2 - \nu_{2i}^2)^\gamma + \rho_{12}(\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma \\ &\leq (p_{12} + q_{12} + \rho_{12}) \max\{(\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma, (\nu_{1i}^2 - \nu_{2i}^2)^\gamma, (\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma\} \\ &= \max\{(\mu_{1i}^2 - \mu_{2i}^2)^\gamma, (\nu_{1i}^2 - \nu_{2i}^2)^\gamma, (\pi_{1i}^2 - \pi_{2i}^2)^\gamma\} \\ &\leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

This leads to the conclusion that $0 \leq \left(1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq 1$.

Similarly, we can establish that $0 \leq \left(\sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq 1$.

We can combine these results to show:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq d_*(U_1, U_2) \leq d^*(U_1, U_2) \leq 1 \\ 0 &\leq \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} + \sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)} \leq 1 \\ 0 &\leq 1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} + \sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)} \leq 1 \\ 0 &\leq \left((1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)})^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)^2 + \left((\sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)})^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)^2 \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

This proves that $s(U_1, U_2) \in \text{PFS}$.

The properties of symmetry, $s(U_1, U_2) = s(U_2, U_1)$, and identity, $s(U_1, U_2) = (1, 0) \Rightarrow U_1 = U_2$, are direct consequences of the symmetric nature of d^* and d_* . A detailed illustration of these proofs can be found in a similar context in [9]. This proves that $s(U_1, U_2) = \left(\left(1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\sqrt[\gamma]{d_*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)$ is a similarity measure for Pythagorean fuzzy sets.

We refer Equation 9 as the probabilistic similarity degree for Pythagorean fuzzy sets.

Theorem 3: Let S be any Pythagorean fuzzy similarity matrix. Then

$$S \rightarrow S^2 \rightarrow S^4 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow S^{2^k} \rightarrow \dots$$

there must exist a least positive integer k such that $S^{2^k} = S^{2^{k+1}}$. Here, we refer S^{2^k} by Pythagorean fuzzy equivalence matrix.

Definition 10: λ -cutting matrix of S where S be an Pythagorean fuzzy similarity matrix, where $s_{ij} = (\mu_{ij}, \nu_{ij})$, $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, p$. Then $S_\lambda = (\lambda s_{ij})$ is called the λ -cutting matrix of S , where

$$\lambda s_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \geq 1 - \nu_{ij}^2 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } \mu_{ij}^2 < \lambda \leq 1 - \nu_{ij}^2 \\ 1 & \text{if } \mu_{ij}^2 \geq \lambda \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Remark 1: Given a collection of PFSs $\bar{U} = \{U_1, \dots, U_p\}$, let S^* be the equivalent similarity matrix derived from S using Theorem 3. Its λ -cut matrix is λS^* . If the i^{th} and j^{th} rows of λS^* are identical, then U_i and U_j belong to the same cluster.

4. Probabilistic Similarity Based Clustering Algorithm for Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets:

Given a set of Pythagorean fuzzy sets $U = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_p\}$ from a universe of discourse, we aim to find its clusters. The methodology proceeds as follows:

First, we compute the probabilistic intervals for membership and non membership using Algorithms 1 and 2. We then calculate the correlation coefficient matrix, ρ . After normalization, these are used to determine d^* and d_* , with the aid of Equations 7 and 8. From these the probabilistic similarity degree for each pair of PFSs is calculated, as detailed in Algorithm 3.

The resulting similarity matrix is then converted into an equivalence matrix via Theorem 3. Finally, we apply λ -cut clustering, as outlined in Algorithm 4, using Equation 10 and Remark 1 to identify distinct cluster structures for different values of λ .

5. Clustering Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets Using a Probabilistic Similarity Measure: A Case Study-

We utilize the car dataset from [9], which is detailed in Table 1. This dataset consists of evaluations for ten newly released cars, denoted as $U = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{10}\}$. Each car is characterized by six features: fuel economy (ω_1), Aerod degree (ω_2), Price (ω_3), Comfort (ω_4), Design (ω_5), and Safety (ω_6). The feature evaluations are provided as Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (IFs), which can also be represented as Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets (PFSs). We employ this dataset to ensure a fair comparison with the results of previously proposed algorithms.

To begin, we compute the probability matrices P and Q . The matrix P , computed using Algorithm 1, is presented in Tables 2 and 3. Similarly, the probability matrix Q , obtained via Algorithm 2, is shown in Tables 4 and 5.

Next, we calculate the PFSs correlation coefficient for each pair of cars (U_i and U_j) for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 10$. The resulting P , Q , and ρ matrices are then normalized. The normalized ρ matrix is provided in Tables 6 and 7.

Using these normalized matrices, we compute the probabilistic similarity degree between each pair of cars, again for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 10$, with the help of Algorithm 3. The results are shown in Tables 8 and 9.

Algorithm 1: Computation of Membership Probability Interval

Input: Membership functions $\mu_{U_j}(\omega_i)$, non-membership $\nu_{U_j}(\omega_i)$, hesitation $\pi_{U_j}(\omega_i)$, $1 \leq i \leq N$, $1 \leq j \leq p$

Output: Probability interval $p_{ij} = [p_{ij}^l, p_{ij}^u]$

for $i = 1$ to N **do**

Compute $\mu'(\omega_i) = \min_j \mu_{U_j}(\omega_i)$

end for

Form set $\mathcal{C} = \{\mu'(\omega_1), \mu'(\omega_2), \dots, \mu'(\omega_N)\}$

Compute $\mathcal{S} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mu'(\omega_i)$

for $i = 1$ to N **do**

if $\mathcal{S} \neq 0$ **then**

$$p(\omega_i) = \frac{\mu'(\omega_i)}{\mathcal{S}}$$

else

$$p(\omega_i) = 1$$

end if

end for

for $j = 1$ to p **do**

$$p_{\min}(U_j) = \sum_{i=1}^N p(\omega_i) \mu_{U_j}^2(\omega_i)$$

$$p_{\max}(U_j) = p_{\min}(U_j) + \sum_{i=1}^N p(\omega_i) \pi_{U_j}^2(\omega_i)$$

Confidence Interval: $[p_{\min}(U_j), p_{\max}(U_j)]$

end for

for each pair (U_i, U_j) **do**

Define $p_{ij}^u = \max(p_{\min}(U_i), p_{\min}(U_j))$

Define $p_{ij}^l = \min(p_{\max}(U_i), p_{\max}(U_j))$

if $p_{ij}^l \leq p_{ij}^u$ **then**

$$p_{ij} = [p_{ij}^l, p_{ij}^u]$$

else

$$p_{ij} = [p_{ij}^u, p_{ij}^l]$$

end if

end for

Algorithm 2: Computation of Non-membership Probability Interval

Input: Membership functions $\mu_{U_j}(\omega_i)$, non-membership $\nu_{U_j}(\omega_i)$, hesitation $\pi_{U_j}(\omega_i)$, $1 \leq i \leq N$, $1 \leq j \leq p$

Output: Probability interval $q_{ij} = [q_{ij}^l, q_{ij}^u]$

for $i = 1$ to N **do**

Compute $\nu'(\omega_i) = \min_j \nu_{U_j}(\omega_i)$

end for

Form set $\mathcal{C} = \{\nu'(\omega_1), \nu'(\omega_2), \dots, \nu'(\omega_N)\}$

Compute $\mathcal{S} = \sum_{i=1}^N \nu'(\omega_i)$

for $i = 1$ to N **do**

if $\mathcal{S} \neq 0$ **then**

$$q(\omega_i) = \frac{\nu'(\omega_i)}{\mathcal{S}}$$

else

$$q(\omega_i) = 1$$

end if

end for

for $j = 1$ to p **do**

$$q_{\min}(U_j) = \sum_{i=1}^N q(\omega_i) \nu_{U_j}^2(\omega_i)$$

$$q_{\max}(U_j) = q_{\min}(U_j) + \sum_{i=1}^N q(\omega_i) \pi_{U_j}^2(\omega_i)$$

Confidence Interval: $[q_{\min}(U_j), q_{\max}(U_j)]$

end for

for each pair (U_i, U_j) **do**

Define $q_{ij}^u = \max(q_{\min}(U_i), q_{\min}(U_j))$

Define $q_{ij}^l = \min(q_{\max}(U_i), q_{\max}(U_j))$

if $q_{ij}^l \leq q_{ij}^u$ **then**

$$q_{ij} = [q_{ij}^l, q_{ij}^u]$$

else

$$q_{ij} = [q_{ij}^u, q_{ij}^l]$$

end if

end for

Algorithm 3: Probabilistic Similarity Degree between PFSs U_1 and U_2

Input: Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets $U_1 = (\mu_{1i}, \nu_{1i}, \pi_{1i})$ and $U_2 = (\mu_{2i}, \nu_{2i}, \pi_{2i})$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$, and parameter $\gamma \geq 1$.

Output: Probabilistic Similarity Degree $s(U_1, U_2) = \left(\left(1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)$

1. Compute Confidence Intervals and Correlation Coefficient:

Use Algorithm 1 to compute p_{12}^l and p_{12}^u for the pair (U_1, U_2) .

Use Algorithm 2 to compute q_{12}^l and q_{12}^u for the pair (U_1, U_2) .

Calculate the correlation coefficient ρ_{12} between U_1 and U_2 using Equation (5).

Let $\rho(U_{12}) = \rho_{12}$ for convenience in subsequent steps.

2. Sum Confidence Intervals for Normalization Factors:

Compute $r_{\min}(U_{12}) = p_{12}^l + q_{12}^l + \rho_{12}$

Compute $r_{\max}(U_{12}) = p_{12}^u + q_{12}^u + \rho_{12}$

3. Calculate Normalized Parameters for $d_*(U_1, U_2)$ (Minimum Distance):

$$p_{12}^- = \min \left\{ \frac{p^l(U_{12})}{r_{\min}(U_{12})}, \frac{p^u(U_{12})}{r_{\max}(U_{12})} \right\}$$

$$q_{12}^- = \min \left\{ \frac{q^l(U_{12})}{r_{\min}(U_{12})}, \frac{q^u(U_{12})}{r_{\max}(U_{12})} \right\}$$

$$\rho_{12}^- = \min \left\{ \frac{\rho(U_{12})}{r_{\min}(U_{12})}, \frac{\rho(U_{12})}{r_{\max}(U_{12})} \right\}$$

4. Calculate Normalized Parameters for $d^*(U_1, U_2)$ (Maximum Distance):

$$p_{12}^+ = \max \left\{ \frac{p^l(U_{12})}{r_{\min}(U_{12})}, \frac{p^u(U_{12})}{r_{\max}(U_{12})} \right\}$$

$$q_{12}^+ = \max \left\{ \frac{q^l(U_{12})}{r_{\min}(U_{12})}, \frac{q^u(U_{12})}{r_{\max}(U_{12})} \right\}$$

$$\rho_{12}^+ = \max \left\{ \frac{\rho(U_{12})}{r_{\min}(U_{12})}, \frac{\rho(U_{12})}{r_{\max}(U_{12})} \right\}$$

5. Compute Probabilistic Distances:

Compute $d_*(U_1, U_2)$ using the calculated $p_{12}^-, q_{12}^-, \rho_{12}^-$ and Equation 8.

Compute $d^*(U_1, U_2)$ using the calculated $p_{12}^+, q_{12}^+, \rho_{12}^+$ and Equation 7.

6. Derive Probabilistic Similarity Degree:

$$\text{Compute } s(U_1, U_2) = \left(\left(1 - \sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\sqrt[\gamma]{d^*(U_1, U_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)$$

Algorithm 4: Clustering Algorithm based on λ -Cut

Input: U collection of p Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets $U = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_p\}$ (each with N features), a parameter $\gamma \geq 1$, and a predefined threshold $\lambda \in [0, 1]$.

Output: Clusters of Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets.

1. Construct Pythagorean Fuzzy Similarity Matrix S :

Initialize an empty $p \times p$ matrix S .

for each pair (U_i, U_j) from U , where $1 \leq i, j \leq p$ **do**

 Compute the probabilistic similarity degree $s(U_i, U_j)$ using Algorithm 3.

end for

2. Derive Pythagorean Fuzzy Equivalence Matrix S^* :

 Compute S^* from S using the iterative process described in Theorem 3.

3. Calculate λ -Cut Matrix λS^* :

 Initialize an empty $p \times p$ binary matrix λS^* .

for $i = 1$ to p **do**

for $j = 1$ to p **do**

 Calculate $(\lambda S^*)_{ij}$ using Equation 10

end for

end for

4. Form Clusters:

 Initialize an empty list of clusters $\mathcal{C} = []$.

 Initialize a list of unassigned PFSs, $U_{unassigned} = \{U_1, \dots, U_p\}$.

while $U_{unassigned}$ is not empty **do**

 Pick an unassigned PFS, say $U_k \in U_{unassigned}$.

 Create a new cluster $C_m = \{U_k\}$.

for $U_j \in U_{unassigned}$ where $j \neq k$ **do**

if the k^{th} row of λS^* is identical to the j^{th} row of λS^* **then**

 Add U_j to C_m .

end if

end for

 Add C_m to \mathcal{C} .

 Remove all PFSs in C_m from $U_{unassigned}$.

end while

return \mathcal{C}

Table 1: Car dataset

	ω_1	ω_2	ω_3	ω_4	ω_5	ω_6
U_1	(0.3,0.4)	(0.2,0.7)	(0.4,0.5)	(0.8,0.1)	(0.4,0.5)	(0.2,0.7)
U_2	(0.4,0.3)	(0.5,0.1)	(0.6,0.2)	(0.2,0.7)	(0.3,0.6)	(0.7,0.2)
U_3	(0.4,0.2)	(0.6,0.1)	(0.8,0.1)	(0.2,0.6)	(0.3,0.5)	(0.5,0.2)
U_4	(0.3,0.4)	(0.9,0.0)	(0.8,0.1)	(0.7,0.1)	(0.1,0.8)	(0.2,0.8)
U_5	(0.8,0.1)	(0.7,0.2)	(0.7,0.0)	(0.1,0.8)	(0.1,0.8)	(0.4,0.6)
U_6	(0.4,0.3)	(0.3,0.5)	(0.2,0.6)	(0.4,0.5)	(0.4,0.4)	(0.5,0.4)
U_7	(0.6,0.4)	(0.4,0.2)	(0.7,0.2)	(0.3,0.6)	(0.7,0.1)	(0.3,0.7)
U_8	(0.9,0.1)	(1.0,0.0)	(1.0,0.0)	(0.0,1.0)	(0.0,1.0)	(0.3,0.6)
U_9	(0.4,0.4)	(0.9,0.1)	(0.9,0.1)	(0.2,0.7)	(0.2,0.7)	(0.1,0.9)
U_{10}	(0.9,0.1)	(0.8,0.0)	(0.6,0.3)	(0.5,0.2)	(0.8,0.1)	(0.6,0.4)

Applying Theorem 3, we establish the Pythagorean fuzzy equivalence relation from the similarity matrix. This equivalence matrix is presented in Tables 10 and 11.

Finally, we perform λ -cut clustering on this Pythagorean fuzzy equivalence matrix using Algorithm 4. This process yields distinct clusters for different values of λ . We used Remark 1 to determine the different values of λ that correspond to distinct cluster structures.

Table 2: Probability Matrix P (Part 1/2)

attribute	U_1	U_2	U_3	U_4	U_5
U_1	(0.1955, 0.7527)	(0.2145, 0.7527)	(0.2636, 0.7527)	(0.3818, 0.7527)	(0.4545, 0.7527)
U_2	(0.2145, 0.7527)	(0.2145, 0.8409)	(0.2636, 0.8409)	(0.3818, 0.8364)	(0.4545, 0.8409)
U_3	(0.2636, 0.7527)	(0.2636, 0.8409)	(0.2636, 0.8718)	(0.3818, 0.8364)	(0.4545, 0.8718)
U_4	(0.3818, 0.7527)	(0.3818, 0.8364)	(0.3818, 0.8364)	(0.3818, 0.8364)	(0.4545, 0.8364)
U_5	(0.4545, 0.7527)	(0.4545, 0.8409)	(0.4545, 0.8718)	(0.4545, 0.8364)	(0.4545, 0.9518)
U_6	(0.1955, 0.7527)	(0.2145, 0.8155)	(0.2636, 0.8155)	(0.3818, 0.8155)	(0.4545, 0.8155)
U_7	(0.2736, 0.7527)	(0.2736, 0.8309)	(0.2736, 0.8309)	(0.3818, 0.8309)	(0.4545, 0.8309)
U_8	(0.5009, 0.7527)	(0.5009, 0.8409)	(0.5009, 0.8718)	(0.5009, 0.8364)	(0.5009, 0.92)
U_9	(0.4427, 0.7527)	(0.4427, 0.8409)	(0.4427, 0.8445)	(0.4427, 0.8364)	(0.4545, 0.8445)
U_{10}	(0.5391, 0.7527)	(0.5391, 0.8409)	(0.5391, 0.8718)	(0.5391, 0.8364)	(0.5391, 0.9518)

Table 8, and Table 9 is similarity matrix after applying Algorithm 3. Using Theorem 3 we derive transitive matrix from Table 8 and Table 9.

Since its already reflexive and symmetric, therefore its equivalence relation matrix.

Table 3: Probability Matrix P (Part 2/2)

attribute	U_6	U_7	U_8	U_9	U_{10}
U_1	(0.1955, 0.7527)	(0.2736, 0.7527)	(0.5009, 0.7527)	(0.4427, 0.7527)	(0.5391, 0.7527)
U_2	(0.2145, 0.8155)	(0.2736, 0.8309)	(0.5009, 0.8409)	(0.4427, 0.8409)	(0.5391, 0.8409)
U_3	(0.2636, 0.8155)	(0.2736, 0.8309)	(0.5009, 0.8718)	(0.4427, 0.8445)	(0.5391, 0.8718)
U_4	(0.3818, 0.8155)	(0.3818, 0.8309)	(0.5009, 0.8364)	(0.4427, 0.8364)	(0.5391, 0.8364)
U_5	(0.4545, 0.8155)	(0.4545, 0.8309)	(0.5009, 0.92)	(0.4545, 0.8445)	(0.5391, 0.9518)
U_6	(0.1873, 0.8155)	(0.2736, 0.8155)	(0.5009, 0.8155)	(0.4427, 0.8155)	(0.5391, 0.8155)
U_7	(0.2736, 0.8155)	(0.2736, 0.8309)	(0.5009, 0.8309)	(0.4427, 0.8309)	(0.5391, 0.8309)
U_8	(0.5009, 0.8155)	(0.5009, 0.8309)	(0.5009, 0.92)	(0.5009, 0.8445)	(0.5391, 0.92)
U_9	(0.4427, 0.8155)	(0.4427, 0.8309)	(0.5009, 0.8445)	(0.4427, 0.8445)	(0.5391, 0.8445)
U_{10}	(0.5391, 0.8155)	(0.5391, 0.8309)	(0.5391, 0.92)	(0.5391, 0.8445)	(0.5391, 0.9582)

Table 4: Probability Matrix Q (Part 1/2)

attribute	U_1	U_2	U_3	U_4	U_5
U_1	(0.14, 0.7033)	(0.3133, 0.7033)	(0.2967, 0.7033)	(0.27, 0.7033)	(0.14, 0.52)
U_2	(0.3133, 0.7033)	(0.3133, 0.9033)	(0.3133, 0.9033)	(0.3133, 0.8033)	(0.3133, 0.52)
U_3	(0.2967, 0.7033)	(0.3133, 0.9033)	(0.2967, 0.9033)	(0.2967, 0.8033)	(0.2967, 0.52)
U_4	(0.27, 0.7033)	(0.3133, 0.8033)	(0.2967, 0.8033)	(0.27, 0.8033)	(0.27, 0.52)
U_5	(0.14, 0.52)	(0.3133, 0.52)	(0.2967, 0.52)	(0.27, 0.52)	(0.02, 0.52)
U_6	(0.14, 0.7)	(0.3133, 0.7)	(0.2967, 0.7)	(0.27, 0.7)	(0.0867, 0.52)
U_7	(0.3367, 0.7033)	(0.3367, 0.82)	(0.3367, 0.82)	(0.3367, 0.8033)	(0.3367, 0.52)
U_8	(0.17, 0.6233)	(0.3133, 0.6233)	(0.2967, 0.6233)	(0.27, 0.6233)	(0.17, 0.52)
U_9	(0.23, 0.7033)	(0.3133, 0.8133)	(0.2967, 0.8133)	(0.27, 0.8033)	(0.23, 0.52)
U_{10}	(0.14, 0.4333)	(0.3133, 0.4333)	(0.2967, 0.4333)	(0.27, 0.4333)	(0.02, 0.4333)

Table 5: Probability Matrix Q (Part 2/2)

attribute	U_6	U_7	U_8	U_9	U_{10}
U_1	(0.14, 0.7)	(0.3367, 0.7033)	(0.17, 0.6233)	(0.23, 0.7033)	(0.14, 0.4333)
U_2	(0.3133, 0.7)	(0.3367, 0.82)	(0.3133, 0.6233)	(0.3133, 0.8133)	(0.3133, 0.4333)
U_3	(0.2967, 0.7)	(0.3367, 0.82)	(0.2967, 0.6233)	(0.2967, 0.8133)	(0.2967, 0.4333)
U_4	(0.27, 0.7)	(0.3367, 0.8033)	(0.27, 0.6233)	(0.27, 0.8033)	(0.27, 0.4333)
U_5	(0.0867, 0.52)	(0.3367, 0.52)	(0.17, 0.52)	(0.23, 0.52)	(0.02, 0.4333)
U_6	(0.0867, 0.7)	(0.3367, 0.7)	(0.17, 0.6233)	(0.23, 0.7)	(0.0867, 0.4333)
U_7	(0.3367, 0.7)	(0.3367, 0.82)	(0.3367, 0.6233)	(0.3367, 0.8133)	(0.3367, 0.4333)
U_8	(0.17, 0.6233)	(0.3367, 0.6233)	(0.17, 0.6233)	(0.23, 0.6233)	(0.17, 0.4333)
U_9	(0.23, 0.7)	(0.3367, 0.8133)	(0.23, 0.6233)	(0.23, 0.8133)	(0.23, 0.4333)
U_{10}	(0.0867, 0.4333)	(0.3367, 0.4333)	(0.17, 0.4333)	(0.23, 0.4333)	(0.02, 0.4333)

6. Comparison With Similar Clustering Algorithm:

In this section, we present a comparative analysis of clustering methods. We compare the results of our proposed probabilistic λ -cut method on Probabilistic Fuzzy Sets (PFSs) with two other techniques: the probabilistic λ -cut method on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (IFSs) and the associative matrix method.

Table 6: The normalized ρ matrix (Part 1/2)

attribute	U_1	U_2	U_3	U_4	U_5
U_1	(0.7488, 0.4072)	(0.5884, 0.3414)	(0.5655, 0.3337)	(0.5352, 0.3401)	(0.5351, 0.3496)
U_2	(0.5884, 0.3414)	(0.6545, 0.3644)	(0.6206, 0.3511)	(0.5028, 0.3001)	(0.4911, 0.3525)
U_3	(0.5655, 0.3337)	(0.6206, 0.3511)	(0.6409, 0.3603)	(0.5397, 0.3267)	(0.5093, 0.359)
U_4	(0.5352, 0.3401)	(0.5028, 0.3001)	(0.5397, 0.3267)	(0.6054, 0.3788)	(0.4986, 0.3470)
U_5	(0.5351, 0.3496)	(0.4911, 0.3525)	(0.5093, 0.359)	(0.4986, 0.3470)	(0.6782, 0.4046)
U_6	(0.7416, 0.3986)	(0.6094, 0.3521)	(0.5834, 0.3411)	(0.5216, 0.3193)	(0.5848, 0.3634)
U_7	(0.5459, 0.3350)	(0.6102, 0.3666)	(0.6098, 0.3662)	(0.4933, 0.2997)	(0.5007, 0.3700)
U_8	(0.4714, 0.3030)	(0.5041, 0.3611)	(0.4989, 0.3469)	(0.4561, 0.3069)	(0.5603, 0.3725)
U_9	(0.4936, 0.3105)	(0.4582, 0.2788)	(0.5077, 0.3151)	(0.5769, 0.3721)	(0.5161, 0.3486)
U_{10}	(0.4725, 0.3390)	(0.4515, 0.3551)	(0.4585, 0.3516)	(0.4442, 0.3374)	(0.6329, 0.4104)

Table 7: The normalized ρ matrix (Part 2/2)

attribute	U_6	U_7	U_8	U_9	U_{10}
U_1	(0.7416, 0.3986)	(0.5459, 0.3350)	(0.4714, 0.3030)	(0.4936, 0.3105)	(0.4725, 0.3390)
U_2	(0.6094, 0.3521)	(0.6102, 0.3666)	(0.5041, 0.3611)	(0.4582, 0.2788)	(0.4515, 0.3551)
U_3	(0.5834, 0.3411)	(0.6098, 0.3662)	(0.4989, 0.3469)	(0.5077, 0.3151)	(0.4585, 0.3516)
U_4	(0.5216, 0.3193)	(0.4933, 0.2997)	(0.4561, 0.3069)	(0.5769, 0.3721)	(0.4442, 0.3374)
U_5	(0.5848, 0.3634)	(0.5007, 0.3700)	(0.5603, 0.3725)	(0.5161, 0.3486)	(0.6329, 0.4104)
U_6	(0.7850, 0.3975)	(0.5680, 0.3462)	(0.4995, 0.3175)	(0.4798, 0.2905)	(0.5278, 0.3590)
U_7	(0.5680, 0.3462)	(0.6210, 0.3772)	(0.5085, 0.3734)	(0.4514, 0.2806)	(0.4622, 0.3732)
U_8	(0.4995, 0.3175)	(0.5085, 0.3734)	(0.5985, 0.3932)	(0.4718, 0.3079)	(0.5606, 0.4006)
U_9	(0.4798, 0.2905)	(0.4514, 0.2806)	(0.4718, 0.3079)	(0.5978, 0.3762)	(0.4641, 0.3426)
U_{10}	(0.5278, 0.3590)	(0.4622, 0.3732)	(0.5606, 0.4006)	(0.4641, 0.3426)	(0.6414, 0.4181)

Table 8: Probabilistic similarity degree matrix (Part 1/2)

attribute	U_1	U_2	U_3	U_4	U_5
U_1	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8353, 0.2566)	(0.8117, 0.3291)	(0.7355, 0.0)	(0.8016, 0.3256)
U_2	(0.8353, 0.2566)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.9117, 0.2088)	(0.8093, 0.2646)	(0.8246, 0.3329)
U_3	(0.8117, 0.3291)	(0.9117, 0.2088)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8075, 0.0)	(0.8412, 0.3208)
U_4	(0.7355, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2646)	(0.8075, 0.0)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8061, 0.3284)
U_5	(0.8016, 0.3256)	(0.8246, 0.3329)	(0.8412, 0.3208)	(0.8061, 0.3284)	(1.0, 0.0)
U_6	(0.9324, 0.2452)	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.8157, 0.2003)	(0.7324, 0.0)	(0.8287, 0.2379)
U_7	(0.8313, 0.3726)	(0.9153, 0.2540)	(0.8939, 0.0)	(0.7692, 0.3134)	(0.8421, 0.2430)
U_8	(0.7175, 0.0)	(0.7659, 0.2710)	(0.7677, 0.2796)	(0.7275, 0.2742)	(0.8496, 0.0)
U_9	(0.5233, 0.2202)	(0.6517, 0.2168)	(0.6778, 0.2161)	(0.8499, 0.2041)	(0.7192, 0.3912)
U_{10}	(0.7123, 0.3757)	(0.7660, 0.1834)	(0.7685, 0.3729)	(0.7252, 0.3147)	(0.9267, 0.1705)

Table 9: Probabilistic similarity degree matrix (Part 2/2)

attribute	U_6	U_7	U_8	U_9	U_{10}
U_1	(0.9324, 0.2452)	(0.8313, 0.3726)	(0.7175, 0.0)	(0.5233, 0.2202)	(0.7123, 0.3757)
U_2	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.9153, 0.2540)	(0.7659, 0.2710)	(0.6517, 0.2168)	(0.7660, 0.1834)
U_3	(0.8157, 0.2003)	(0.8939, 0.0)	(0.7677, 0.2796)	(0.6778, 0.2161)	(0.7685, 0.3729)
U_4	(0.7324, 0.0)	(0.7692, 0.3134)	(0.7275, 0.2742)	(0.8499, 0.2041)	(0.7252, 0.3147)
U_5	(0.8287, 0.2379)	(0.8421, 0.2430)	(0.8496, 0.0)	(0.7192, 0.3912)	(0.9267, 0.1705)
U_6	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8702, 0.3926)	(0.7531, 0.2612)	(0.5307, 0.2117)	(0.7419, 0.3932)
U_7	(0.8702, 0.3926)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.1868)	(0.6016, 0.2165)	(0.8272, 0.2891)
U_8	(0.7531, 0.2612)	(0.8462, 0.1868)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.7312, 0.4048)	(0.8516, 0.0)
U_9	(0.5307, 0.2117)	(0.6016, 0.2165)	(0.7312, 0.4048)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.7605, 0.2584)
U_{10}	(0.7419, 0.3932)	(0.8272, 0.2891)	(0.8516, 0.0)	(0.7605, 0.2584)	(1.0, 0.0)

Table 10: The computed Pythagorean fuzzy equivalence matrix (Part 1/2)

attribute	U_1	U_2	U_3	U_4	U_5
U_1	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_2	(0.8766, 0.0)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.9117, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_3	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.9117, 0.0)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_4	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)
U_5	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(1.0, 0.0)
U_6	(0.9324, 0.0)	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_7	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.9153, 0.0)	(0.9117, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_8	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8516, 0.0)
U_9	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8499, 0.2041)	(0.8093, 0.2041)
U_{10}	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.9267, 0.0)

Table 11: Pythagorean fuzzy equivalence matrix (Part 2/2)

attribute	U_6	U_7	U_8	U_9	U_{10}
U_1	(0.9324, 0.0)	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_2	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.9153, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_3	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.9117, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_4	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.0)	(0.8499, 0.2041)	(0.8093, 0.0)
U_5	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8516, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.9267, 0.0)
U_6	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8766, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_7	(0.8766, 0.0)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8462, 0.0)
U_8	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8516, 0.0)
U_9	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(1.0, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)
U_{10}	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8462, 0.0)	(0.8516, 0.0)	(0.8093, 0.2041)	(1.0, 0.0)

Table 12 displays the clusters obtained using our method. Table 13 shows the results from the probabilistic λ -cut method on IFSs [9], and Table 14 presents the clusters found using the associative matrix method [22] on IFSs.

A key difference is observed when comparing our approach with the associative matrix method. For instance, in Table 14, the associative matrix method initially separates $\{U_2\}$ and $\{U_3, U_7\}$ for $0.861 \leq \lambda \leq 0.889$. However, for a higher λ range ($0.889 \leq \lambda \leq 0.919$), these clusters merge to form $\{U_2, U_3, U_7\}$. In contrast, our algorithm ensures that as λ increases, clusters only split and do not merge.

Furthermore, our method provides a more detailed decomposition of clusters compared to the probabilistic λ -cut method on IFSs (Table 13). For example, our algorithm successfully identifies the cluster $\{U_5, U_8, U_{10}\}$, which is not found using the IFS-based method.

Table 12: Clustering results for Pythagorean fuzzy sets

λ level	Clustering results
$0 \leq \lambda < 0.655$	$\{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5, U_6, U_7, U_8, U_9, U_{10}\}$
$0.655 \leq \lambda < 0.716$	$\{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_5, U_6, U_7, U_8, U_{10}\}, \{U_4, U_9\}$
$0.716 \leq \lambda < 0.7223$	$\{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_6, U_7\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5, U_8, U_{10}\}$
$0.7223 \leq \lambda < 0.7253$	$\{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_6, U_7\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5, U_8, U_{10}\}, \{U_9\}$
$0.7253 \leq \lambda < 0.7684$	$\{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_6, U_7\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}$
$0.7684 \leq \lambda < 0.8312$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_3, U_7\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}$
$0.8312 \leq \lambda < 0.8379$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_7\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}$
$0.8379 \leq \lambda < 0.8587$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}$
$0.8587 \leq \lambda < 0.9583$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.9583 \leq \lambda \leq 1.0$	$\{U_1\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_6\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}, \{U_{10}\}$

Table 13: [9] Clustering results for Intuitionistic fuzzy sets

λ level	Clustering results
$0 \leq \lambda \leq 0.59$	$\{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5, U_6, U_7, U_8, U_9, U_{10}\}$
$0.59 < \lambda \leq 0.64$	$\{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_5, U_6, U_7, U_8, U_{10}\}$
$0.64 < \lambda \leq 0.70$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_2, U_3, U_5, U_7, U_8, U_{10}\}$
$0.70 < \lambda \leq 0.74$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_3, U_7, U_8\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}$
$0.74 < \lambda \leq 0.77$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_3, U_7\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}, \{U_8\}$
$0.77 < \lambda \leq 0.82$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_3\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}$
$0.82 < \lambda \leq 0.83$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_3\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.83 < \lambda \leq 0.86$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.86 < \lambda \leq 0.91$	$\{U_1\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_6\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.91 < \lambda \leq 1.00$	$\{U_1\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_6\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}, \{U_{10}\}$

Table 14: [22] Clustering results for Intuitionistic fuzzy sets (association matrix)

λ level	Clustering results
$0 \leq \lambda < 0.709$	$\{U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5, U_6, U_7, U_8, U_9, U_{10}\}$
$0.709 \leq \lambda \leq 0.771$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5, U_7, U_8, U_9, U_{10}\}$
$0.771 \leq \lambda \leq 0.811$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3, U_5, U_7, U_{10}\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_4, U_9\}$
$0.811 \leq \lambda \leq 0.861$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3, U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5, U_{10}\}$
$0.861 \leq \lambda \leq 0.889$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3, U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.889 \leq \lambda \leq 0.913$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2, U_3, U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.913 \leq \lambda \leq 0.919$	$\{U_1, U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3, U_7\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.919 \leq \lambda \leq 0.937$	$\{U_1\}, \{U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3, U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.937 \leq \lambda \leq 0.968$	$\{U_1\}, \{U_6\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_4, U_9\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_{10}\}$
$0.968 \leq \lambda \leq 1.000$	$\{U_1\}, \{U_2\}, \{U_3\}, \{U_4\}, \{U_5\}, \{U_6\}, \{U_7\}, \{U_8\}, \{U_9\}, \{U_{10}\}$

7. Conclusion and Future Work:

This paper introduces a novel probabilistic similarity measure specifically for Pythagorean fuzzy sets (PFSs). This measure is used to construct an equivalence relation matrix, from which a new λ -cut method is derived for clustering.

When applied to a car dataset, our algorithm produced more refined and representative clusters than existing methods. It is important to note that for a fair comparison, we used a dataset that is traditionally considered intuitionistic fuzzy, as a probabilistic similarity measure for intuitionistic fuzzy sets cannot be directly applied to a larger Pythagorean fuzzy dataset.

This highlights a key advantage of our method: its applicability to larger datasets that fall under Pythagorean fuzzy framework. However, its higher computational cost limits scalability to larger datasets.

Future work will focus on evaluating the algorithm across diverse datasets and developing approximation techniques to reduce computational complexity, aiming to extend its applicability to larger-scale problems.

References:

- [1] L.A. Zadeh : Similarity relations and fuzzy orderings, *Information sciences* 3 (2) (1971), 177-200.
- [2] Z. Peng, Y. Sun : *Fuzzy mathematics and its application*, Wu Han University Press, China (2007), 4-10.
- [3] M.-S. Yang : A survey of fuzzy clustering, *Mathematical and Computer modelling* 18 (11) (1993), 1-16.
- [4] G.-S. Liang, T.-Y. Chou, T.-C. Han : Cluster analysis based on fuzzy equivalence relation, *European Journal of Operational Research* 166 (1) (2005), 160-171.
- [5] L. Hongxing : Fuzzy clustering methods based on perturbation, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 33 (3) (1989), 291-302.
- [6] Z. Chai : A study of clustering on optimal fuzzy equivalence relations, *Soft Computing* 27 (3) (2023), 1415-1424.
- [7] K.T. Atanassov : Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, in: *Intuitionistic fuzzy sets: theory and applications*, Springer, 1999, pp. 1-137.

- [8] B. Li, W. He : The structures of intuitionistic fuzzy equivalence relations, *Information Sciences* 278 (2014), 883-899.
- [9] Q.D. Lohani, R. Solanki, P.K. Muhuri : Novel adaptive clustering algorithms based on a probabilistic similarity measure over atanasov intuitionistic fuzzy set, *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems* 26 (6) (2018), 3715-3729.
- [10] N.X. Thao, M. Ali, F. Smarandache : An intuitionistic fuzzy clustering algorithm based on a new correlation coefficient with application in medical diagnosis, *Journal of intelligent & fuzzy systems* 36 (1) (2019), 189-198.
- [11] P.A. Ejegwa : Modified and generalized correlation coefficient between intuitionistic fuzzy sets with applications, *Notes on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets* 26 (1) (2020), 8-22.
- [12] J. Bajaj, S. Kumar : A new intuitionistic fuzzy correlation coefficient approach with applications in multi-criteria decision-making, *Decision Analytics Journal* 9 (2023), 100340.
- [13] X. Zhang : Pythagorean fuzzy clustering analysis: a hierarchical clustering algorithm with the ratio index-based ranking methods, *International Journal of Intelligent Systems* 33 (9) (2018), 1798-1822.
- [14] X. Peng, G. Selvachandran : Pythagorean fuzzy set: state of the art and future directions, *Artificial Intelligence Review* 52 (3) (2019), 1873-1927.
- [15] R.R. Yager : Extending set measures to pythagorean fuzzy sets, *International Journal of Fuzzy Systems* 21 (2) (2019), 343-354.
- [16] R.R. Yager : Pythagorean fuzzy subsets, in: 2013 joint IFSA world congress and NAFIPS annual meeting (IFSA/NAFIPS), IEEE, 2013, pp. 57-61.
- [17] W.A. Wilson : On quasi-metric spaces, *American Journal of Mathematics* 53 (3) (1931), 675-684.
- [18] D. Guha, D. Chakraborty : A new approach to fuzzy distance measure and similarity measure between two generalized fuzzy numbers, *Applied Soft Computing* 10 (1) (2010), 90-99.

- [19] T. Gerstenkorn, J. Mańko : Correlation of intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 44 (1) (1991), 39-43.
doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/01650114\(91\)90031-K](https://doi.org/10.1016/01650114(91)90031-K)
URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/016501149190031K>
- [20] B. Agheli, M. Adabitarbar Firozja, H. Garg : Similarity measure for pythagorean fuzzy sets and application on multiple criteria decision making, *Journal of Statistics and Management Systems* 25 (4) (2022), 749-769.
- [21] H. Garg : A novel correlation coefficients between pythagorean fuzzy sets and its applications to decision-making processes, *International Journal of Intelligent Systems* 31 (12) (2016), 1234-1252.
- [22] H.-m. Zhang, Z.-s. Xu, Q. Chen : On clustering approach to intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Control and Decision* 22 (8) (2007), 882.